

EFFECTIVENESS OF MINDFULNESS-BASED COGNITIVE THERAPY ON TEST ANXIETY AND EMOTION REGULATION AMONG SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN EDO STATE

Osahon Isoken Maris

*Department of Educational Evaluation and Counselling Psychology, Faculty of Education,
University of Benin, Benin-City*

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16982279>

Keywords:
*Effectiveness,
Cognitive
Therapy,
Mindfulness-
Based Cognitive
Therapy, Test
Anxiety, Emotion
Regulation*

Abstract: *This paper investigated the effectiveness of mindfulness-based cognitive therapy on test anxiety and emotional regulation among senior secondary school students in Edo State. Two research questions guided the study while two null hypotheses were formulated at 0.05 alpha level. The study adopted a quasi-experimental design specifically the pre-test, post-test control group design. The study participants included 231 male and female SS two students in two selected schools in Oredo Local Government of Edo State. The experimental group school was systematically exposed to Mindfulness-Based Cognitive Therapy (MBCT) over a duration of four weeks. Instrument for data collection was an adopted questionnaire titled Test Anxiety Inventory (TAI) developed by Spielberger (1980) and Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (ERQ) developed by Gross and John (2003). Descriptive statistics such as means, standard deviations were employed to answer the research questions while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA), was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level. The findings revealed that students in the experimental group demonstrated greater improvements in reducing test anxiety and enhancing emotion regulation compared to those in the control group. The hypotheses were confirmed, showing that MBCT significantly lowered test anxiety and improved emotion regulation. Based on the findings, it was recommended amongst others that secondary schools in Edo State integrate mindfulness-based cognitive therapy into their guidance and counseling services. School counselors and psychologists should be trained in MBCT techniques to help students manage exam-related stress and anxiety effectively.*

Introduction

Secondary education is a crucial stage in a child's educational progression in Nigeria, providing further educational and vocational opportunities for completion of primary education. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) defines

secondary education as the bridge between primary and tertiary education, preparing students for useful living within society and higher education, laying the foundation for academic and career pursuits at the tertiary level. Secondary education is of strategic importance to

Osahon Isoken Maris

Nigerian development and capacity building, as it is a conduit for individual and societal progress. In Edo State, like in many other parts of the country, senior secondary schools not only prepare students for the rigors of higher education but also for high-stakes external examinations such as the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) and the National Examination Council (NECO) examinations. These examinations are often perceived as gateways to future opportunities, determining admission into universities.

Consequently, students in this stage experience enormous academic pressure, as their performance is viewed not only as a personal achievement but also as a reflection of family expectations, societal standards, and the investments made by their schools (Aihie & Adeyemi, 2024). The authors further stressed that while this pressure can serve as motivation for some learners, for many others it translates into heightened levels of worry, tension, and fear, which may undermine their ability to concentrate, prepare effectively, or perform optimally during tests. It is within this high-stakes environment that the issue of anxiety, particularly test anxiety, becomes a pressing concern among secondary school students in Edo State, thereby linking the discourse of education to the psychological experiences that accompany it.

Anxiety refers to a state in which a person is overly worried and upset about the occurrence of a terrible event in the future. Test anxiety is a specific form of anxiety that arises in evaluative situations, particularly when individuals are assessed through tests or examinations. It is

characterized by feelings of tension, apprehension, and worry that interfere with performance. According to Burton and Baxter (2019), test anxiety is an emotional state experienced in evaluative situations, characterized by worry, tension, and apprehension about the possible negative consequences of poor performance. Similarly, Brown et al., (2019) defined test anxiety as the phenomenological, physiological, and behavioural responses surrounding concern about possible negative consequences or failure in an evaluative situation. Operationally, test anxiety is the heightened psychological, emotional, and physiological response experienced by senior secondary school students in Edo State when preparing for or engaging in test or examination situations, which interferes with their ability to concentrate, regulate emotions, and perform effectively.

The reasons why students develop test anxiety in school settings are multifaceted and often rooted in the educational context. High-stakes examinations such as WASSCE and NECO create pressure as they serve as determinants of future academic and career opportunities (Owens, Stevenson, Hadwin & Norgate, 2012). According to Ilo and Unachukwu (2020), students feel anxious because they perceive tests as threatening events that may expose their inadequacies or result in failure. Family expectations and peer comparisons further compound this pressure, as many learners internalize the fear of disappointing significant others (Putwain, 2009). In Edo State, Aihie and Adeyemi (2024) observed that secondary school students report moderate to high levels of

anxiety stemming from parental demands for success, limited preparation time, and fear of academic failure. These findings underscore that test anxiety is not just an individual problem but one embedded in the broader social and academic demands placed on students (Ullrich, Goetz, Voracek, Krannich, Bieg, Jarrell & Pekrun, 2021). In this regard, test anxiety can be seen not merely as a problem of over-arousal but as a reflection of difficulties in managing worry, fear, and stress in evaluative situations.

Emotion regulation has been defined in contemporary scholarship in diverse but complementary ways. Gross (2015) defined it as the processes by which individuals influence which emotions they have, when they have them, and how they experience and express them. More recently, Aldao, Nolen-Hoeksema, and Schweizer (2010) described it as the set of strategies people use to increase, maintain, or decrease their emotional experiences across situations. Similarly, Webb, Miles, and Sheeran (2012) defined emotion regulation as goal-directed processes to modify the occurrence, intensity, or duration of emotional states to promote adaptive outcomes. For the purpose of this study, emotion regulation is operationally defined as the capacity of senior secondary school students in Edo State to manage and modulate their emotional responses during examinations and school-related activities, in ways that either enhance or hinder their ability to function and achieve academically.

During daily school activities such as classroom participation, homework, or group work, effective emotion regulation enables students to remain engaged, recover from setbacks, and

persist with challenging tasks. In contrast, poor regulation often manifests in withdrawal, procrastination, and heightened stress when faced with evaluative tasks or teacher feedback. In examination-heavy settings such as senior secondary schools in Nigeria, students' regulatory strategies become critical determinants of both academic performance and mental wellbeing. The present situation in Edo State underscores the importance of emotion regulation among secondary school students. Aihie and Adeyemi (2024) reported that many students in Egor Local Government Area displayed moderate to high levels of test-related anxiety, and this anxiety was often compounded by limited coping skills and poor regulation strategies. This finding suggests that while students recognize the high stakes of examinations, they are often ill-equipped to manage the emotional demands associated with them. Broader Nigerian studies also indicate that many adolescents rely heavily on maladaptive strategies such as suppression and avoidance, which not only maintain anxiety but also heighten stress over time (Ugwu & Ojukwu, 2019). When regulation strategies are ineffective, anxiety persists and undermines performance; when adaptive strategies are cultivated, students are more resilient, focused, and capable of meeting academic challenges. Recognizing the current gaps in students' emotion regulation abilities highlights the need for interventions such as Mindfulness-Based Cognitive Therapy. Mindfulness-Based Cognitive Therapy (MBCT) represents a thoughtful blend of traditional cognitive behavioral therapy principles with mindfulness practices, designed to help people

navigate their inner experiences more skillfully. At its core, MBCT encourages individuals to cultivate present-moment awareness through techniques like meditation, breathing exercises, and body scans, while also examining and reframing unhelpful thought patterns that can fuel emotional distress (Priebe & Kurtz-Costes, 2022). The usefulness of MBCT lies in its ability to interrupt cycles of negative thinking and emotional reactivity, making it a powerful tool for long-term well-being. By promoting mindfulness, it helps people recognize early signs of distress and respond with compassion rather than automatic rumination, which can prevent issues from escalating. Research shows it significantly reduces the risk of depression relapse and eases symptoms of anxiety and stress, allowing individuals to build resilience and improve overall quality of life (Yilmazer, Hamamci & Turk, 2024).

Building on these, MBCT shows promising effectiveness in curbing test anxiety among students, a common barrier that can erode confidence and performance during examination (Pickerell, Pennington, Cartledge, Miller & Curtis, 2023). By teaching mindfulness techniques, it helps students observe anxious thoughts—such as fears of failure—without letting them spiral, leading to reduced physiological symptoms like rapid heartbeat or mental fog. A meta-analysis revealed that mindfulness-based interventions, including MBCT variants, have a moderate to large effect in lowering test anxiety levels, enabling better focus and calmer responses under pressure (Priebe & Kurtz-Costes, 2022). Similarly, studies on college students demonstrate that even short

online MBCT programmes correlate with decreased test anxiety reports, as participants gain tools to manage pre-exam jitters more adaptively (Yilmazer, et al., 2024).

This ties directly into MBCT's role in enhancing emotion regulation, which is crucial for students facing academic pressures that often amplify feelings like frustration or overwhelm. Through regular practice, MBCT strengthens neural pathways for emotional awareness and modulation, helping young people shift from reactive states to more deliberate, compassionate responses (Zheng, Li, Liu, Li & Hou, 2024). The authors reported that interventions have been found to boost mindfulness levels and reduce psychological distress while improving emotion regulation strategies, with effects sustained over follow-up periods.

Succinctly, it is important to note that the pressing reality that senior secondary school students in Edo State face intense academic and social pressures, often culminating in heightened test anxiety and poor emotional regulation. Examinations such as WASSCE and NECO, are not only academic assessments but also deeply psychological events. For many students, inadequate coping skills and reliance on maladaptive strategies such as suppression or avoidance exacerbate stress, undermining both performance and well-being. While existing studies (Aihie & Adeyemi, 2024; Ugwu & Ojukwu, 2019) have documented the prevalence of anxiety among Nigerian adolescents, fewer have explored structured psychological interventions that directly address both test anxiety and emotion regulation within this context.

Osahon Isoken Maris

Mindfulness-Based Cognitive Therapy (MBCT) emerges as a promising approach for filling this gap. Research in other regions has consistently shown that MBCT reduces anxiety, improves attention, and enhances adaptive emotion regulation (Priebe & Kurtz-Costes, 2022; Zheng et al., 2024). Yet, despite the growing global evidence base, its application among secondary school populations in Nigeria, and specifically in Edo State, remains underexplored. This creates a critical research gap, that this study filled.

Statement of the Problem

In Edo State, senior secondary school students are faced with the enormous pressure of preparing for and excelling in high-stakes examinations such as the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE), National Examination Council (NECO), and Joint Admissions and Matriculation Board (JAMB) examinations. Many students experience intense test anxiety, manifested through restlessness, difficulty concentrating, racing thoughts, and physical symptoms such as rapid heartbeat and sweating. Research in Nigeria has consistently revealed that test anxiety is prevalent among secondary school students, with significant negative consequences for their academic performance and psychological well-being.

The problem is further compounded by poor emotion regulation skills among these students. Adolescents often lack the psychological tools to manage overwhelming emotions such as fear, worry, and self-doubt during examinations. Many resort to maladaptive strategies, including suppression or avoidance, which exacerbate distress rather than relieve it. This vulnerability

has been observed in Edo State, where teachers and parents report that otherwise intelligent students perform below expectations simply because they are unable to control their anxiety during test situations. The inability to effectively regulate emotions does not only affect academic outcomes but also contributes to long-term stress, diminished self-esteem, and reduced motivation to learn. Despite the prevalence of this problem, current school interventions in Edo State remain largely academic in nature, focusing on remedial teaching, extra lessons, or motivational talks. These strategies fail to address the psychological roots of test anxiety and emotional dysregulation. This creates a critical gap for the introduction of structured psychological interventions that target both cognition and emotional responses to stress. Mindfulness-Based Cognitive Therapy (MBCT), which integrates principles of mindfulness and cognitive restructuring, has been shown internationally to reduce anxiety, enhance emotional awareness, and promote adaptive coping strategies. However, its application among Nigerian secondary school students, particularly in Edo State, has received little empirical attention. It is therefore against this backdrop that this study investigated the effectiveness of mindfulness-based cognitive therapy on test anxiety and emotion regulation among senior secondary school students in Edo State. Specifically, the study determined:

1. The effectiveness of mindfulness-based cognitive therapy on test anxiety among senior secondary school students in Edo State

2. The effectiveness of mindfulness-based cognitive therapy on emotion regulation among senior secondary school students in Edo State

Research Questions

1. What is the effectiveness of mindfulness-based cognitive therapy on test anxiety among senior secondary school students in Edo State?
2. What is the effectiveness of mindfulness-based cognitive therapy on emotion regulation among senior secondary school students in Edo State?

Hypotheses

1. Mindfulness-based cognitive therapy does not have a significant effect on test anxiety among senior secondary school students at pre-test and post-test stages.
2. Mindfulness-based cognitive therapy does not have a significant effect on emotional regulation among senior secondary school students at pre-test and post-test stages.

Methodology

Research Design

The study adopted a quasi-experimental design specifically the pre-test, post-test control group design. This design was considered appropriate because it allowed the researcher to determine the effectiveness of Mindfulness-Based Cognitive Therapy (MBCT) on test anxiety and emotion regulation among secondary school students, while at the same time comparing outcomes between an experimental group that received treatment and a control group that did not.

Participants

The study participants included 231 male and female SS two students in two selected schools in Oredo Local Government of Edo State. The first school consisting of 114 students (53 males and

61 females) was used as the experimental group while the second school consisting of 117 students (49 males and 68 females) was used as the control group.

Treatment Procedure

The experimental group school was systematically exposed to Mindfulness-Based Cognitive Therapy (MBCT) over a duration of four weeks. The intervention consisted of structured sessions facilitated by trained professionals, focusing on mindfulness practices such as breathing exercises, guided meditation, body scans, and cognitive restructuring techniques. The sessions were organized twice weekly, each lasting between 40–50 minutes, and were integrated into the students' academic schedule without disrupting regular classroom activities. The MBCT program was designed to help students develop awareness of their thoughts, identify and regulate negative automatic thinking patterns, and adopt healthier coping mechanisms for test-related anxiety. In contrast, the control group school was not exposed to any treatment during the period of the study. The students in this group continued with their regular classroom activities without any form of mindfulness training or therapeutic intervention. This created a clear distinction between both groups, ensuring that any observed difference in outcomes could be attributed to the MBCT intervention.

Instruments for Data Collection

Test Anxiety Inventory (TAI): This scale, developed by Spielberger (1980), was used to measure the level of test anxiety among students. It consists of 20 items designed to capture worry and emotionality components of test anxiety.

The instrument has been widely validated in diverse educational settings, including Nigeria, and has demonstrated high reliability coefficients. Spielberger (1980) originally reported a Cronbach's alpha of .92 for the overall scale, with subscale reliabilities of .91 (Worry) and .90 (Emotionality). Studies in Nigeria (Oluwatelure & Adesemowo, 2005) also confirm the cultural applicability of the TAI, reporting Cronbach alpha values of above **.85**, showing strong reliability in local educational settings.

Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (ERQ): Developed by Gross and John (2003), this instrument was employed to measure students' ability to regulate their emotions. ERQ has 10 items assessing two key dimensions: cognitive reappraisal and expressive suppression. Responses are rated on a 7-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 = strongly disagree to 7 = strongly agree. The ERQ has been validated in multiple cultural contexts, including African populations, where it retained acceptable psychometric properties (Matsumoto et al., 2008). Gross and John (2003) reported high internal consistency for both subscales: Cognitive Reappraisal: Cronbach's $\alpha = .79$ to $.82$; Expressive Suppression: Cronbach's $\alpha = .73$ to $.76$

Procedure for Data Collection

Pre-Test Phase: Before the commencement of the MBCT intervention, both the experimental and control group students were administered the Test Anxiety Inventory (TAI) and the Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (ERQ) as a pre-test. This provided a baseline measure of their test anxiety levels and emotion regulation strategies.

Intervention Phase: The experimental group was exposed to MBCT sessions twice weekly for four weeks, facilitated by the researcher and trained assistants. Each session combined mindfulness practices with cognitive restructuring exercises, while encouraging students to practice mindfulness informally during their daily academic activities. The control group, on the other hand, received no intervention.

Post-Test Phase: At the end of the four-week intervention, both groups were re-administered the same instruments (TAI and ERQ) to assess changes in test anxiety and emotion regulation.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics such as means, standard deviations were employed to answer the research questions while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA), was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level.

Results

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation on the effectiveness of mindfulness-based cognitive therapy on test anxiety among senior secondary school students in Edo State

Group	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean gain
		\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	
MBCT	114	35.45	2.89	71.07	2.66	35.62
Control	117	21.51	2.76	50.89	2.68	29.38
Mean Difference						6.24

The result in Table 1 shows that students in the experimental group (MBCT) recorded higher improvements in test anxiety reduction compared to the control group. At pre-test, the MBCT group had a mean score of 35.45, which significantly increased to 71.07 at post-test, with

a mean gain of 35.62. In contrast, the control group improved from 21.51 at pre-test to 50.89 at post-test, with a mean gain of 29.38. The mean difference between groups (6.24) indicates that MBCT was more effective in reducing test anxiety

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation on the effectiveness of mindfulness-based cognitive therapy on emotion regulation among senior secondary school students in Edo State

Group	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean gain
		\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	
MBCT	114	39.72	3.09	69.23	2.10	29.51
Control	117	30.93	2.83	47.41	2.44	16.48
Mean Difference						13.03

Table 2 indicates that mindfulness-based cognitive therapy (MBCT) significantly improved students' emotion regulation compared to the control group. At pre-test, the MBCT group had a mean score of 39.72, which rose to 69.23 at post-test, yielding a mean gain of 29.51. Conversely, the control group improved from 30.93 at pre-test to 47.41 at post-test, with a

lower mean gain of 16.48. The mean difference of 13.03 between the groups demonstrates that MBCT was more effective in enhancing students' ability to regulate emotions, highlighting its positive impact on managing emotional responses among senior secondary school students.

Table 3: ANCOVA analysis of mindfulness-based cognitive therapy significant effect on test anxiety among senior secondary school students at pre-test and post-test stages.

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p
Covariate	210.84	1	210.84	11.24	.001
Group	2170.37	1	2170.37	115.72	.000
Error	4342.28	227	19.13		
Total	13457.66	229			

Data presented in Table 3 reveals an analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was conducted to examine the effectiveness of Mindfulness-Based Cognitive Therapy (MBCT) on test anxiety among senior secondary school students in Edo State, while controlling for pre-test scores. Results revealed a significant main effect of group, $F(1, 227) = 115.72, p < .001$, indicating a

large effect size. This shows that, after adjusting for pre-test differences, students who participated in MBCT reported significantly lower levels of test anxiety at post-test compared to their counterparts in the control group. Therefore, MBCT was effective in reducing test anxiety.

Table 4: ANCOVA analysis of mindfulness-based cognitive therapy significant effect on emotional regulation among senior secondary school students at pre-test and post-test stages.

Source	SS	Df	MS	F	p
Covariate	640.28	1	640.28	61.45	< .001
Group	1475.67	1	1475.67	141.22	< .001
Error	2371.21	227	10.45		
Total	8123.16	229			

Data presented in Table 4 reveals that analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was conducted to determine the effect of mindfulness-based cognitive therapy (MBCT) on emotion regulation among senior secondary school students in Edo State, while controlling for pre-test scores. The results revealed a significant main effect of group on post-test emotion regulation, $F(1, 227) = 141.22, p < .001$. This indicates that students exposed to MBCT had significantly higher

emotion regulation scores compared to their counterparts in the control group, even after adjusting for initial differences.

Discussion of Findings

The finding in research question one revealed that students in the experimental group (MBCT) recorded higher improvements in test anxiety reduction compared to the control group. The corresponding hypothesis also revealed that students who participated in MBCT reported

significantly lower levels of test anxiety at post-test compared to their counterparts in the control group in secondary schools in Edo State. This finding agreed with the finding of Nzeadibe, Egara, Eseadi, and Chukwuorji (2024) that after 12 sessions over six weeks, saw their anxiety scores drop dramatically from around 55 to 32 by follow-up, while the control group's scores stayed virtually unchanged. This highlights how targeted mindfulness practices can break the cycle of worry, leading to lasting improvements that outpace standard counselling. The finding of Eneogu et al., (2025) reported that mindfulness-based interventions, including those like MBCT, produced a moderate to large reduction in test anxiety overall, with effect sizes showing clear advantages for the intervention groups over controls. This is particularly relevant for students, as the average age in these studies was about 19, suggesting mindfulness helps curb the mental blocks that exams often trigger across educational levels.

The finding in research question two revealed that mindfulness-based cognitive therapy (MBCT) significantly improved students' emotion regulation compared to the control group in secondary schools in Edo State. The corresponding hypothesis revealed that students exposed to MBCT had significantly higher emotion regulation scores compared to their counterparts in the control group in secondary schools in Edo State. This finding supported that of Cotton, et al., (2020) that MBCT group demonstrated associations between increased mindfulness and improved emotion regulation, unlike the control group, suggesting MBCT's role in bolstering regulatory skills amid emotional

challenges. This finding also corroborated with that of Bluth, Gaylord, Campo, Mullarkey and Hoobs (2016) that participants in the MBCT-adapted intervention showed notable enhancements in emotion regulation, highlighting how structured mindfulness can reduce dysregulation and promote calmer responses to stress. Similarly, the findings of Broderick and Metz (2009) conducted a pilot trial of the Learning to BREATHE curriculum, an MBCT-inspired program, for adolescents. The intervention group exhibited significant improvements in emotion regulation compared to controls, with reductions in negative affect and better coping strategies, underscoring MBCT's potential for everyday emotional balance in school settings.

Conclusion

This study investigated the effectiveness of mindfulness-based cognitive therapy (MBCT) on test anxiety reduction and emotion regulation among senior secondary school students in Edo State. It was therefore concluded that students in the experimental group demonstrated greater improvements in reducing test anxiety and enhancing emotion regulation compared to those in the control group. The hypotheses were confirmed, showing that MBCT significantly lowered test anxiety and improved emotion regulation. These results underscore the potential of MBCT as an effective psychological intervention for promoting students' mental well-being and academic performance, thereby highlighting its relevance in secondary school settings in Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Since MBCT significantly reduced test anxiety among students, it is recommended that secondary schools in Edo State integrate mindfulness-based cognitive therapy into their guidance and counseling services. School counselors and psychologists should be trained

REFERENCES

- Aihie, O. N., & Adeyemi, F. T. (2024). *Emotional intelligence and test anxiety among secondary school students in Egor locality of Edo State, Nigeria. Maldives National Journal of Research*, 12(1), 1–12. <https://mnu.edu.mv/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/MNJR-Vol.-12-No.-1-2024-3.pdf>
- Aldao, A., Nolen-Hoeksema, S., & Schweizer, S. (2010). Emotion regulation strategies across psychopathology: A meta-analytic review. *Clinical Psychology Review*, 30(2), 217–237. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpr.2009.11.004>
- Bluth, K., Gaylord, S. A., Campo, R. A., Mullarkey, M. C., & Hobbs, L. (2016). Making friends with yourself: A mixed methods pilot study of a mindful self-compassion program for adolescents. *Mindfulness*, 7(2), 479–492. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12671-015-0476-6>
- Broderick, P. C., & Metz, S. (2009). Learning to BREATHE: A pilot trial of a mindfulness curriculum for adolescents. *Advances in*

in MBCT techniques to help students manage exam-related stress and anxiety effectively.

2. As MBCT improved students' emotion regulation, teachers and school administrators in Edo State should adopt mindfulness practices as part of classroom and co-curricular activities. This will equip students with lifelong emotional coping strategies, fostering resilience, positive mental health, and improved academic outcomes.

School Mental Health Promotion, 2(3), 35–46.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/1754730X.2009.9715696>

- Brown, L.A., Forman, E.M., Herbert, J.D., Hoffman, K.L., Yuen, E.K., & Goetter, E.M. (2019). A randomized controlled trial of acceptance-based behavior therapy and cognitive therapy for test anxiety: A pilot study. *Behavior modification*, 35(1), 31–53.
- Burton, B.N., & Baxter, M.F. (2019). The Effects of the Leisure Activity of Coloring on Post-Test Anxiety in Graduate Level Occupational Therapy Students. *The Open Journal of Occupational Therapy*, 7(1), 7–15.
- Cotton, S., Luberto, C. M., Sears, R. W., Strawn, J. R., Stahl, L., Wasson, R. S., Blom, T. J., & DelBello, M. P. (2020). Mindfulness-based cognitive therapy for youth with anxiety disorders at risk for bipolar disorder: A pilot trial. *Early Intervention in Psychiatry*, 14(2), 221–234. <https://doi.org/10.1111/eip.12891>
- Eneogu, N. D., Ezech, O. H., Ugwu, U. C., Eseadi, C., Ugwuanyi, C. S., Obochi, W. L., Nweke,

- M. L., Nnamani, O., Nwafor, B. N., Okeke, F. C., & Nwobi, N. L. (2025). Impact of cognitive-behavioral therapy and mindfulness-based stress reduction in mitigating test anxiety and enhancing academic achievement among vocational education students at Nigerian universities. *BMC Medical Education*, *25*, Article 1063. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-025-07130-w>
- Gross, J. J. (2015). Emotion regulation: Current status and future prospects. *Psychological Inquiry*, *26*(1), 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1047840X.2014.940781>
- Gross, J. J., & John, O. P. (2003). *Individual differences in two emotion regulation processes: Implications for affect, relationships, and well-being*. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, *85*(2), 348–362. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.85.2.348>
- Ilo, D. C., & Unachukwu, G. C. (2020). Test anxiety as predictor of senior secondary school students' achievement in English and Mathematics in Anambra State. *Socialscientia Journal of the Social Sciences and Humanities*, *5*(1), 72–82.
- Matsumoto, D., Yoo, S. H., Nakagawa, S., & Multinational Study of Cultural Display Rules. (2008). *Culture, emotion regulation, and adjustment*. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, *94*(6), 925–937. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.94.6.925>
- Nzeadibe, A. C., Egara, F. O., Eseadi, C., & Chukwuorji, J. B. C. (2024). Mindfulness-based cognitive therapy for mathematics anxiety among school adolescents: A randomised trial. *Journal of Psychologists and Counsellors in Schools*, *34*(1), 42–53. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20556365231207248>
- Oluwatelure, T. A., & Adesemowo, P. O. (2005). Test anxiety and academic performance in Nigeria: Validity of Spielberger's Test Anxiety Inventory. *African Journal of Educational Research*, *11*(1&2), 1–8.
- Owens, M., Stevenson, J., Hadwin, J. A., & Norgate, R. (2012). Anxiety and depression in academic performance: An exploration of the mediating factors of worry and working memory. *School Psychology International*, *33*(4), 433–449. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0143034311427433>
- Pickerell, L. E., Pennington, K., Cartledge, C., Miller, K. A., & Curtis, F. (2023). The effectiveness of school-based mindfulness and cognitive behavioural programmes to improve emotional regulation in 7–12-year-olds: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Mindfulness*, *14*(6), 1269–1294. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12671-023-02131-6>
- Priebe, N. P., & Kurtz-Costes, B. E. (2022). The effect of mindfulness programs on collegiate test anxiety. *Mindfulness*, *13*(11), 2853–2863.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12671-022-02002-6>

Putwain, D. W. (2009). Assessment and examination stress in Key Stage 4. *British Educational Research Journal*, 35(3), 391–411.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/01411920802044404>

Spielberger, C. D. (1980). *Test Anxiety Inventory: Preliminary professional manual*. Consulting Psychologists Press.

Ugwu, C. J., & Ojukwu, M. O. (2019). Emotional intelligence, test anxiety and academic performance of secondary school students in Nigeria. *International Journal of Psychology and Counselling*, 11(3), 24–32.

<https://doi.org/10.5897/IJPC2019.0564>

Ullrich, A.-L., Goetz, T., Voracek, M., Krannich, M., Bieg, M., Jarrell, A., & Pekrun, R. (2021). Test anxiety and physiological arousal: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Educational Psychology Review*, 33(2), 579–618.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-020-09543-z>

Webb, T. L., Miles, E., & Sheeran, P. (2012). Dealing with feeling: A meta-analysis of the effectiveness of strategies derived from the process model of emotion regulation. *Psychological Bulletin*, 138(4), 775–808.

Yilmazer, E., Hamamci, Z., & Türk, F. (2024). Effects of mindfulness on test anxiety: A meta-analysis. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 15, Article 1401467.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1401467>

Zheng, Q., Li, J., Liu, Y., Li, Y., & Hou, Y. (2024). The effectiveness of mindfulness-based intervention for psychological distress and emotion regulation in college students with non-suicidal self-injury. *Applied Psychology: Health and Well-Being*. Advance online publication.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/aphw.12580>